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Designing an Integrated Approach to Realizing Communicative Self-Efficacy in Engineering Communication

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ABSTRACT

Abstract

Given the escalating demands for “work-ready” undergraduates plus the heavy workload of engineering faculty and students, adding effective communications instruction to the engineering curriculum is a significant challenge. In response to that challenge, the Sibley School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (MAE) and the Engineering Communications Program (ECP) at Cornell University have begun to develop a new communications curriculum. The new curriculum has two components: 1) partnering a sophomore-level mechanical engineering course teaching mechanical design principles with an engineering communications course; and 2) integrating focused communication units in select junior and senior level MAE courses. Our aim is twofold. First, we hope that partnering these two courses will offer a more impactful and expertise appropriate way to deliver communications instruction. Second, we also hope that implementing a coordinated communication-across-the-curriculum (CxC) effort will better meet the needs of students, faculty, the college and industry.

This new (and still developing) curriculum, named the “MAE/ECP Engineering Communications Initiative,” is a collaborative and cooperative enterprise encouraging the development of students' communicative self-efficacy (CSE) across a range of engineering communicative genres. Four foundational concepts are our benchmarks: communication as social action, the importance of context, communicative design, and engineering identity. Both the partnering and coordinated communications modules are continually assessed through a multi-year, mixed-methods research program. The first years' quantitative findings for the communications course show noteworthy increases in CSE, with the second year's quantitative findings reportable by conference time.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Engineering Communication

Keywords: Engineering Communication, Communicative Self-Efficacy, Curricular Integration and Assessment, Educational Research

Introduction

Engineering communication is ubiquitous in the lives of professional engineers and engineering students alike. Recent surveys indicate that engineers spend between 40 and 60 percent (and more) of their workday engaged in communicative activities [1-4], and anecdotal reports suggest an even higher percentage. And while many admit that effective communication is a core skill set of any adept engineer, too frequently curricula siphon off communication skills into a less-than category, too often called “soft skills,” hinting (sometimes declaring) that other engineering skills are harder and more valued.

We challenge that thinking at its very core in our work teaching engineering communication inside a US college of engineering. Almost all job postings for entry-level engineers require “excellent communication skills, both written and verbal.” Beyond entry-level jobs, employers assume good communication skills are in place, and people who rise quickly through the management ranks tell us that it is their communication skills that make them stand out. As well, experienced engineers or engineering managers often highlight not only the relevance of communication, but also the diverse range of communicative actions that they must perform in order to get work done. [5].

The challenge of infusing communication skills into technical-leaning courses in any engineering curriculum can be a difficult proposition. Most engineering curricula are already heavily burdened with core courses and specialized, field-specific content; so adding direct and recurring communications instruction to an engineering curriculum represents a significant challenge.

Responding to that challenge, some engineering programs are experimenting with creative and engaging ways to develop communication skills. One such experiment is the fostering and use of teaching “partnerships” that tap into the expertise appropriate skills of the technical specialist/engineering instructor and the technical communication instructor respectively. With these kinds of positive partnerships, course content can realign towards “socially situated [technical *and* professional] practice” [6], while also possibly reducing workload for that engineering instructor. The Sibley School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (MAE) and the Engineering Communications Program (ECP) in the College of Engineering at Cornell University are actively facilitating the formation of such a partnership.

We discuss our theoretical and pedagogical underpinnings, teaching approach, and quantitatively report the outcomes of our first year teaching the partnered communications course. By conference time, we will have data to share from our second year.

1 Background: The MAE/ECP Engineering Communications Initiative

The Sibley School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (MAE) currently requires its majors fulfill a college mandated technical communications requirement via its senior level (year 4) capstone lab course. The communication component relies primarily on lab reports and designing visuals. The engineering instructors do successfully empower students to produce good reports and well-designed visuals. However, departmental descriptive surveys, e.g., those involving students, alumni, industry representatives, suggested that MAE needed to do something more to

prepare students for workplace and research communication needs. Indeed, MAE openly wondered if there might be a better way.

In search of this better way, the MAE department, in concert with the college's Engineering Communications Program (ECP), identified a number of important needs. Communication instruction should:

- begin sooner in the MAE curriculum; the aim is a coordinated and constant development of communication skills across the curriculum;
- cover multiple modes – written, oral, visual, electronic (WOVE); the intent is to encourage the transfer of communication skills across technical and professional endeavors;
- empower students to experience the integration of technical and professional practice and develop skills such as iterative revision, peer response; they should be ready to learn to learn how and to teach each other;
- build on single set of theoretically established and foundational concepts:
 - **Communicative Practice:** When we communicate, we perform specific social actions. All communication has one or more purposes.
 - **Communicative Context:** Communicative practice cannot be separated from context nor the context from practice.
 - **Communicative Design:** Communication is all about the particulars of design or structure and organization.
 - **Communicative Identity:** Communication creates identity, not only the identity of the one initiating communicative interaction, but also the identity or identities the one or ones being communicated with.

Rather quickly it became clear that to be able to realize these needs, MAE and ECP together needed to create a new MAE communications curriculum and devise a research program for assessment. The core design of the effort is this: one dedicated, engineering communications partnered with a (preferably design) MAE course at the sophomore level; integrated, focused communication units inside select junior and senior courses.

The sophomore communications course, ENGR 2250, launched in spring 2016, had 20 self-selecting MAE undergraduates enrolled. Quantitative *and* qualitative research was done in parallel. We framed our research question thus:

How well can we facilitate the development of communicative self-efficacy (CSE)?

Or...more closely drawn:

How well can we facilitate in MAE undergraduate engineering students the development of communicative self-efficacy (CSE) through ENGR 2250 and then foster its continuing development through select junior (level 3) and senior (level 4) courses in the MAE curriculum in a way that transfers to and enables proficient technical and professional communicative practice?

We propose that the MAE/ECP Engineering Communications Initiative innovates in a number of ways:

1. It offers both a horizontal and vertical curriculum that is theoretically consistent for providing communication instruction. It potentially offers a model for other schools and colleges of engineering.
2. It anticipates and enables learning to learn how in post-graduate technical and professional communication by providing students experience applying those

foundational concepts within different contexts, using multiple modalities (WOVE) and across many genres.

3. It proposes a model program for near- and long-term assessment through locally-situated and emergent educational research.

2 Research mandate, self-efficacy, and methods

Briefly put, we designed our research protocols pragmatically. We needed to study the impact of communication instruction upon undergraduate students in an engineering curriculum. After much work, we formulated an explanatory, sequential mixed methods design, i.e., survey along with classroom participant observation, interviews, and portfolios. All data collection was institutionally IRB approved.

We built our survey around discovering reports of student communicative self-efficacy (CSE). In choosing to do so, we participate in a well-established practice in engineering education. Self-efficacy (SE) measurements capture how well subjects (in this case, undergraduate students) rate themselves as having positive behaviors; consequently, positive behaviors translate into higher-performing practices. In ASEE (American Society for Engineering Education) Proceedings alone, there are over 1400 references to self-efficacy in student engineering practice. The *European Journal of Engineering Education* boasts 70+ articles about self-efficacy in engineering students in the last decade alone. Self-efficacy is an established and useful construct based originally in Social Cognitive Theory [9]. It “refers to beliefs in one’s capabilities to organize and execute those courses of action required to produce given attainments” [10], or a “person’s awareness of their ability to accomplish a goal” [11]. As a research construct, SE has proven to be a powerful predictor of achievement in general areas—general learning, academic achievement, retention, mathematics – and more specific areas – computing [11], engineering design [12], engineering modeling [13], even tinkering [14] to list just a few. Implementing CSE requires development of a survey instrument, which, although not easy, allows us to generate quantifiable results and to avoid (quite frankly) those prohibitively time- and labor-intensive alternatives for assessing communicative performance. As a result, and along with other possible contributions, our research has the opportunity to offer a model for the development of other similarly focused assessment instruments.

MAE students enrolled in ENGR 2250 took two identical surveys—at the start and end of term. Also, and for the purposes of comparison, the survey was distributed to other sophomore, junior and senior level students across the larger MAE curriculum at the start of the term. Details on method and data tables of results are at

<https://sites.coecis.cornell.edu/chec/ecp-research/>.

3 WOVE: Actionable and socially constructed modes

WOVE is the acronym for the written, oral, visual and electronic modes of communication. It is an emerging research area for engineering education [5]. For our Initiative, specifically, we focused on the particular genres and those modes most important for undergraduate and sophomore level students enrolled in the MAE program.

WOVE elements do not exist in a vacuum [6]. Lab reports almost always include visuals: graphs, tables, charts, sketches. Engineers and scientists might use LaTeX coding to convey equations inside of email. Visuals include strong captions, which involves a specialized style of writing that helps readers decode the graphical input.

Oral presentations bring speech, visuals, writing, and performance together. In truth, it is hard to find engineering or scientific work that exists in just one mode. Indeed, even student project teams thrive in the multimodal milieu: speech, of course, but that communication also involves email exchanges, texts/texting, drawing, and more.

By creating ENGR 2250, we devised work cycles that encouraged the students to develop facility with each of the isolated modes, but they were also developing facility to combine different modes into a single communicative genre given the modality's relative affordances or potentialities and constraints or challenges.

4 Brief overview of the teaching partnership

Students in the mechanical engineering course are required to design a wind/water pump from basic, inexpensive materials that can move a specific volume of water powered by wind, with constraints for cost, etc. Those pump projects are a stand-alone project; students work in teams and do not have to configure a pump system beyond materials, design, and the ability to move a certain amount of water in a given time in a lab setting.

In order to make the experience in the partnered communications course *more authentic* and to encourage *real mastery experiences* (the most significant factor in improving SE generally and CSE specifically), the pump design project became the cornerstone of a larger vision of the place of engineering in solving localized problems. ENGR 2250 asked that students explore ways in which good engineering design is always contextualized, answering the needs of a set of specific set of circumstances that are economically, environmentally, socially, and politically bound. Halfway into the semester, students began intense work that focused on team dynamics, functionality, and workflow, followed quickly with the teams' proposals for their projects. Teams chose a community that was water-poor and placed their designed pumps in that site (in theory). Written proposals plus a presentation required that each team to identify its target community for pump placement and define the wind/water pump solution that could best fit localized need. In addition those student teams produced final reports and gave presentations based on those reports.

Providing a context for the wind/water pump was an essential step in the journey for students, moving from the classroom + lab to the "real world." As well as communicating their technical work on the pump mechanism developed in their mechanical engineering course, the communication project charged teams with the investigative tasks of identifying a community in need, contextualizing water access problems, exploring the history of the community and its water needs, and delving into the aspects (as best they could) that reflect the social justice challenges of engineering. As teaching partners, our motive was to have students experience, even on a small scale, the complex process of moving a technological invention out of the lab and into a demanding situation that was impacted by those opportunities and challenges that every professional engineer encounters. Along the way, we asked them to examine, reflect upon, write about, present, and explore the communication strategies and channels needed for strong work and project deployment.

5 Results of the quantitative survey regarding student communicative self-efficacy (CSE), start of semester

Herein, we provide a quick overview of our research results from the 2016 findings. Our extensive data set (Tables 1-14) is provided fully at <https://sites.coecis.cornell.edu/chec/ecp-research/>.

Perhaps the most important result, at least as it pertains to the quantitative study of CSE, is that the survey instrument that we designed is valid. We know that “validity is not [merely] a property of an instrument” [16], or the answer to the statistical question – does the survey actually measure what it is supposed to measure? Rather, it is revealed by whether or not the resulting scores provide a reasonable and useful representation the subject/topic under investigation. We assert that our data do provide such a representation both for how MAE undergraduates understand their ability to communicate for engineering work and how they understand that that ability develops.

So, what is that representation? Our survey results from the general undergraduate MAE student population shows that CSE increases both for individual survey items and across the various modalities or WOVE as experience increases. That is, the mean scores of seniors exhibit higher CSE than juniors and juniors higher than sophomores. This increase suggests that students understand that their ability to communicate is a **learned experience** that increases with **deepening disciplinary involvement, advancing academic level** and is enhanced through **opportunities to practice**. However, the increase in CSE between the sophomore and junior levels is relatively trivial. The average improvement of the mean scores for individual items is 1.3 points and 1.7 for modalities respectively on a 100 pt. scale. Indeed, there is even some regression. And, the increase between junior and senior levels is modest: 7.5 for individual items and 7.2 for modalities. Knowing that for these undergraduate engineering students CSE does increase, albeit incrementally and not without regression, is important for two reasons. First, understanding that students do improve with disciplinary involvement and advancing level and through practice reinforces the value of each of these factors. Second, understanding that that improvement is limited suggests that there may be (indeed should be) a better way to enhance that improvement.

In comparison with the general MAE undergraduate population, the ENGR 2250 students report a threefold improvement in CSE. And, since the time points for the baseline and the follow-up surveys are the beginning and the end of the term, we attribute that increase to their experience in the course. Specifically, the survey revealed increases in the mean CSE scores both for individual items, approximately 26, and across the various modalities or WOVE, also approximately 26. On the individual survey items, nearly 46% of all MAE students rate themselves as high, between 80 and 100 on the survey scale; while 81% percent of the students who completed the communications course rate themselves as high. For modalities, the percentages are similar: 44% for all MAE students and 84% for ENGR 2250 students. The average mean CSE scores for all students at the end of the communications course is 90 for both individual items and modalities. This score becomes even more impressive when we note that only 23% of students in the baseline survey rate themselves as high. Finally, the average change between the minimum score on each of the items in the baseline and the minimum score on each of the items in the follow-up survey is 42 points. To highlight just one item: we asked students to rate their CSE as to whether they could, “give effective

talks/presentations.” At the start of the semester, the mean score was 55.4. At the end of the term, the same question provided a mean score of 91.7 again on a 100pt scale.

The data we collected (available at [redacted URL]) clearly reveals that changes in CSE are significant for students in the communications course. The single most important takeaway is that there is indeed **a better way!** The only caveat is that our research-to-date is based on a small sample, and it will be important to replicate these patterns and their associated intensities in future distributions of the survey.

7 Conclusion and Next Steps

We piloted the partnering of two courses in an attempt to create a more impactful and expertise appropriate way to deliver communications instruction. And, assuming that CSE is a legitimate means to assess that more impactful and expertise appropriate way, we found that the partnered communications course dramatically increases undergraduate students’ CSE scores. Moving forward, we are keen to learn if their CSE continues to grow, stabilize, or decrease. Using our validated survey tool, we will be able to track such findings.

To review, there are three direct outcomes from the quantitative study: 1) We have a valid instrument to measure CSE, 2) The general population of MAE students show minor improvements in CSE advancing through their senior year, and 3) Students who did take the partnered communications course show a threefold increase in CSE when compared with students who did not. Consequently, we feel safe asserting that direct and recurring instruction and possibly the mastery experiences that result from that instruction leads to significantly greater improvement in CSE. We also feel safe asserting that the curricular model that we have developed for enhancing students’ communicative abilities has potential.

While our research is still very preliminary, there is also an important and emerging question that will merit continuing study. Because those students who have taken ENGR 2250 are familiar with the foundational concepts related to communication, because they are strategic users of the modalities, across a range of contexts while assuming new communicative/professional identities, and finally, because they have high CSE — are ready to learn to learn how to communicate? Are ready to engage in those behaviors that transfer well into professional practice and lead to communicative success? We will rely on our qualitative data and continuing research to answer this question.

Currently, our plan is to continue to foster and expand our teaching partnerships with MAE faculty across the curriculum by offering communication units in select junior and senior level courses. The impact will all the more be strengthened if we can reinforce the idea that good, thoughtful communication is, as we claim, **ubiquitous**. Working with the assumption that our approach to near- and long-term assessment can enable not only MAE but also other engineering schools and departments to offer concrete learning outcomes and produce actual data to support those outcomes, we will be continuing partnerships in the College and potentially in other departments, as well.

We believe that we have made a promising start toward planning and implementing an alternative communications curriculum that empowers students to be stronger communicators and therefore better representatives of the university and assets to their future employers. Of course, we move forward carefully and intentionally, as we are so early in the research process and pull from such a small sample size. Nevertheless, it is safe to suggest that the partnered ENGR 2250 course resulted in

positive and trackable impacts about students' reported communicative self-efficacy (CSE) in engineering contexts while providing for those students a way to experience communication as an integral component of engineering work.

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